

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE GROUNDS AND METHODS FOR THE EMERGENCE OF PROPERTY RIGHTS

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Annotation

This article provides an in-depth exploration of the foundations and methods for the emergence of property rights within civil law. It examines the various legal facts and criteria that govern how property rights come into existence and how they are transferred, focusing on the original and derivative methods of acquiring property rights. The article highlights the distinct nature of legal facts that create, modify, or terminate legal relationships, and further clarifies that these facts operate as grounds for establishing property rights.

Key words:Property Rights, Civil Law, Original Method, Inheritance, Found Property, Yields, Legal Inheritance, Derivative Method, Legal Possession. The grounds for the emergence and termination of property rights are based on the economic and political system of a particular society, as well as the legal system that exists within it. As a result of the influence of these factors, the types and scope of the emergence and termination of property rights may vary.

The grounds and methods for the emergence of property rights have an independent meaning, and these concepts require separate study.

It is well known that legal facts that create, modify, or terminate legal relationships also perform the functions of creating, modifying, and terminating legal rights. The facts that perform the functions of creating rights, as outlined by civil law, are considered the grounds for the emergence of civil law relationships.

The Grounds for Acquiring Property Rights

From this perspective, the grounds for acquiring property rights are various legal facts that lead to the emergence of property rights in relation to certain property, as provided by law. These legal facts, in turn, are the foundations for the establishment of property rights.

An analysis of Chapter 15 of the Civil Code, which lists such legal facts, reveals the following grounds for the emergence of citizens' private property rights:

- The creation and increase of property as a result of labor activities, entrepreneurship, and other economic activities carried out by citizens;

- The sale, exchange, gift, rent, and lifetime maintenance agreements involving the transfer of property (such as real estate) to another person, as well as other transactions not prohibited by law;
- Inheritance, privatization of state property, the duration of ownership that creates the right of ownership, and other legal grounds not conflicting with the law.

The grounds for the establishment of property rights (titles) are usually acquired through two methods during the development of civil law: the original and derivative methods.

According to legal scholars, in such viewpoints, the full legal significance of the original and derivative methods has not been completely considered. On the contrary, in the current civil legislation, problematic situations that arise when property rights are transferred to another person through these methods are finding their solutions.

When discussing the legal nature of the original and derivative methods of acquiring property rights, it is important to note that they are delimited in a specific manner. In legal literature, two main criteria are generally used for this distinction: the will (intent) and legal inheritance criteria. The choice of which criterion to apply for differentiation is not only of theoretical significance but also has important practical implications.

Inheritance in property law refers to the transfer of this right from one subject to another through the derivative method. The basis (legal fact) for such a transfer includes transactions aimed at alienating property, such as sales, exchanges, gifts, and other agreements, as well as inheritance. Only in the derivative method does legal inheritance occur when property rights are acquired. In the original method, there is no legal inheritance because the acquisition of property rights is not dependent on the rights of the former owner.

In certain cases provided by law, legal inheritance may occur independently of the former owner's will (intent). Specifically, individuals who have the right to a mandatory share of the inheritance—such as minor or incapacitated children, including adopted children, as well as the incapacitated spouse and parents, including those who have adopted the deceased—inherit regardless of the testator's will. Undoubtedly, in such cases, inheritance is also considered a derivative method of acquiring property rights.

Property rights often arise at the time of creating something new. In accordance with the law and other legal acts, an individual acquires rights over something

they have created or produced for themselves. If a person loses their right of ownership over their property or abandons or disposes of it voluntarily, another person may acquire ownership rights over that property based on legal grounds. In such cases, the emergence of ownership rights over the property does not depend on the ownership rights of the previous owner. This method of acquiring property rights is referred to as the original method.

The original methods of acquiring property rights are characterized by a common feature: they are not dependent on the rights of the previous owner. Therefore, the procedure for acquiring property rights through the original method is determined by law, rather than by an agreement between the former and the new owner.

In the original method, citizens typically acquire private property rights through the creation of new objects, the results of production activities, or by taking possession of property. Both of these cases fall under the original methods from the perspective of legal inheritance, because in these cases, the rights of the person acquiring the property are not connected to the rights of the previous owner, and no prior rights over the object exist—meaning they arise for the first time.

The basis for acquiring private property rights over created or produced property by citizens includes the following:

a) Creation and multiplication of new property as a result of entrepreneurial and other economic activities; b) Obtaining products, yields, and other income through the use of property in economic or other ways; c) Processing (specification); d) Building a private house on a land plot allocated to citizens in the prescribed manner; e) Acquiring property rights over buildings constructed without authorization.

During the course of entrepreneurial and other economic activities, citizens acquire property rights over various products, yields, and income obtained from property they own. The production of goods, income, and products from property is the ultimate result of citizens' production and economic activities.

The concepts of yield, income, and products differ from one another. Yields refer to items that are directly separated from objects through natural methods. Examples include the fruits from fruit trees, milk and calves from cows, wool from sheep, and other similar products. Therefore, yields are not the results of direct production activities by citizens, but rather the outcomes of the natural state of the objects themselves.

Income, often referred to as civil yields, arises when objects are involved in civil transactions such as leases, loans, and other contracts. In this case, income is generated when the property is provided to another person under a contract. Examples of this include rent paid to the owner for using an object, interest paid to a bank on deposited funds, and dividends from shares. Such yields and income, unless otherwise stipulated by law or contract, belong to the property owner.

Furthermore, property rights over yields can also be acquired by a person who does not own the property but has an independent property right over the object that generates the yield. For example, different types of yields obtained from land plots bequeathed under the right of perpetual possession would belong to the holder of that right. The property rights over yields in this case do not depend on the rights of the actual property owner, and thus the acquisition of property rights over such yields is considered an original method.

In civil transactions, there are instances where objects might not be in the hands of their rightful owners or legal possessors but could be in the hands of illegal possessors. According to civil law theory, illegal possessors are divided into those who are just and those who are unjust, depending on how they acquired the property. Under these conditions, the objects that produce different types of yields may fall under the possession of illegal possessors. The acquisition of property rights over the yields produced from these objects depends on whether the possessor is just or unjust. If the possessor is an unjust possessor, any yields derived from the objects can be claimed by the rightful owner or legal possessor, and property rights will arise in accordance with the law.

In cases where an illegal possessor is a just possessor, the rights to the yields are treated differently from those of an unjust possessor. A just possessor, who knows or should have known that their possession is unlawful, will have ownership of the yields produced from the object up to the time of their recognition of the unlawful nature of their possession. These yields are considered the property of the just possessor, not the true owner. In this case, the acquisition of property rights over the yields follows the original method of acquisition, since the just possessor's rights are based on the law, not the owner's consent, and thus it is classified as an original method of acquiring property rights.

Thus, to conclude, the acquisition of property rights over a found object arises based on a specific legal structure and is considered one of the original methods of acquiring private property rights by citizens. At the same time, in legal

literature, the acquisition of property rights over a found object through the original method is disputed by some scholars.

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